

Antibiotics in Endodontics (Part II)

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The selection of a specific antibiotic is generally based on empirical criteria and on the types of bacteria most frequently isolated from periapical lesions, which are often facultative or anaerobic in nature. Culturing for identification and antibiotic susceptibility testing are advised especially for medically compromised and immunocompromised patients. Even then, empirical administration should be initiated as the identification and susceptibility tests may take some time to report back, ranging from a few days to several weeks. The sampling should be undertaken meticulously to prevent contamination. Both the collection and transfer of samples to the laboratory must be made under strict measures in order to prevent misleading results.

Systemic antibiotic use in the treatment of traumatic injuries of the teeth

Dental injuries are common especially amongst younger individuals. In these cases, prevention of bacterial contamination is of great concern as the prognosis may be dramatically affected, particularly when bacteria are able to access the site of injury and compromise healing. Inflammatory root resorption is one of the most undesirable complications associated with traumatic injuries. Thus, exclusion or limitation of the bacterial load during the healing phase is a logical approach to obtain the best outcomes in the management of traumatic injuries. From current knowledge and based on the International Association of Dental Traumatology (IADT) guidelines, the following recommendations can be made in terms of antibiotic administration following traumatic dental injuries-

Traumatic injury	Systemic antibiotics as adjunct	Type of antibiotic
Tooth fracture	NO	–
Concussion, Subluxation	NO	–
Luxation injuries of permanent dentition	NO	–
Extrusion	NO	–
Replantation of avulsed teeth	YES	Tetracycline, Doxycycline

Luxation injuries of the permanent dentition

IADT guidelines do not recommend the use of systemic antibiotics in the management of luxation injuries or in teeth with root fractures. On the other hand, antibiotic administration might be indicated at the discretion of the clinician when the injury is accompanied by soft tissue trauma requiring intervention. In some cases, the medical status of the patient may also require antibiotic administration.

Replantation of avulsed teeth

Current guidelines recommend systemic antibiotic therapy for patients with avulsion of a permanent tooth, which is replanted. The IADT guidelines state that although the significance of systemic antibiotic administration has not yet been demonstrated by clinical studies, positive effects have been shown in periodontal and pulpal healing in experimental studies, specifically using topical application.

In conclusion, systemic antibiotic administration, in compliance with the age and weight of the patient, may be a useful adjunct for avulsed permanent teeth. On the other hand, in traumatic injuries other than avulsion, such as fracture or luxation injuries, antibiotic administration does not appear to offer any additional advantage unless the patient's medical status or the degree of soft tissue injury necessitate its application.

Topical antibiotic use in endodontics

The use of topical antibiotics has been proposed for several endodontic treatments:

Pulp capping

Dental pulp capping procedures include the application of a protective agent to an exposed pulp (direct capping) or retaining a thin layer of dentine over a nearly exposed pulp (indirect capping) in order to allow the pulp to recover and maintain its normal status and function. Although several clinicians and researchers have used topical antibiotics in pulp capping there is no scientific evidence to support the use of antibiotics in pulp capping procedures. On the contrary, MTA or other calcium silicate-based materials should be used once the cause of the disease (e.g. caries) has been addressed.

Root canal treatment

The risk of adverse effects following systemic application and the ineffectiveness of systemic antibiotics in some pulpal and periapical conditions has led to the use of locally applied antibiotics in root canal treatment, that is within the canal system. The first reported locally used antibiotic product was a polyantibiotic paste containing penicillin, bacitracin, streptomycin and caprylate sodium.

Taking into account that endodontic infections are polymicrobial, tetracyclines (tetracycline HCl, minocycline, demeclocycline, doxycycline), a group of broad-spectrum antibiotics that are effective against a wide range of microorganisms, have been proposed as intracanal topical antibiotics. Sato et al demonstrated the penetration through dentine and the antibacterial efficacy of a mixture of minocycline, a tetracycline, with ciprofloxacin and metronidazole, placed in root canals previously irrigated ultrasonically. Molander et al demonstrated that intracanal clindamycin offers no advantage over conventional calcium hydroxide root canal dressing. BioPure MTAD, a mixture of doxycycline, citric acid and a detergent (Tween 80), has been proposed as a final irrigant because of its numerous properties: antimicrobial activity, smear layer- and pulp-dissolving capability, effect on dentine and adhesion, and biocompatibility (Torabinejad et al). However, microorganisms isolated from root canals have resistance against this group of antibiotics and tetracyclines may promote fungal growth.

Abbott et al demonstrated that when placed in the root canal, the concentration and effectiveness of 3.2% demeclocycline were significantly reduced in peripheral dentine and in the apical third over time. In addition to limited antimicrobial activity tetracyclines cause discolouration of teeth when used as a medicament in root canals. Septomixine forte is another commercial product for intracanal use. It contains two antibiotics, neomycin and polymyxin B sulphate, but the effect against endodontic flora is not better than with calcium hydroxide.

The use of topical antibiotics in root canal treatment has also been proposed to prevent or reduce postoperative symptoms. However, antibiotics do not reduce the pain or swelling arising from teeth with symptomatic apical pathosis.

In summary, use of topical antibiotics during root canal treatment is not supported by the evidence.

Regenerative endodontic procedures

Murray et al. defined regenerative endodontic procedures (REPs) as biologically based procedures designed to replace damaged structures, including dentine and root structures, as well as cells of the pulp–dentine complex. In immature teeth with necrotic pulps and open apices, REPs promote root development and apical closure. Most REPs include minimal-to-no mechanical debridement, relying on chemical debridement and on the use of intracanal medicaments to achieve disinfection. Therefore, intracanal medicaments have been used in almost all published case reports.

Antibiotics used in regenerative endodontic procedures

The antibiotic mixture composed of ciprofloxacin, metronidazole and minocycline ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of each antibiotic, $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of mixture) known as triple antibiotic paste (TAP) or '3mix' has to date been the most widely used intracanal medicament in REPs.

The nitroimidazole compound metronidazole is known for its broad spectrum and strong antibacterial activity against anaerobic cocci, as well as gram-negative and gram-positive bacilli. Metronidazole permeates bacterial cell membranes, reaches the nuclei and binds to the DNA, disrupting its helical structure, causing cell death. Metronidazole has excellent activity against anaerobes isolated from odontogenic abscesses. Moreover, the use of metronidazole has been advocated because of its low induction of bacterial resistance.

Minocycline is a bacteriostatic and broad-spectrum antimicrobial. It is effective against both gram-positive and gram-negative microorganisms, including most spirochetes and many anaerobic and facultative bacteria. Minocycline has been used in periodontal therapy, being available in many topical forms.

The synthetic fluoroquinolone ciprofloxacin has very potent activity against gram-negative pathogens, but its activity is limited against gram-positive bacteria, and most anaerobic bacteria are resistant to ciprofloxacin. Consequently, ciprofloxacin is often combined with metronidazole in the treatment of mixed infections.

Side effects of antibiotics used in regenerative endodontic procedures

The use of antibiotics as intracanal dressings in REP may promote several side effects. A problem that often accompanies the intracanal use of TAP containing minocycline is dentine discoloration suggested substituting minocycline for cefaclor in the tri-antibiotic formula to avoid dentine discoloration, and Miller et al confirmed that the incorporation of cefaclor into TAP, instead of minocycline, avoided discoloration.

Antibiotics and dental pulp stem cells

The preservation of host residual cells is essential for favourable REP outcomes. Stem cells must survive to contribute to tissue regeneration. The mixture of ciprofloxacin, metronidazole and minocycline has been demonstrated to be well tolerated by vital pulp tissues. Moreover, the effect of TAP on subcutaneous tissue over different time periods has been evaluated, concluding that it is biocompatible. The TAP concentration used in regenerative endodontic procedures ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ each antibiotic) is highly effective against endodontic bacteria and is nontoxic to stem cells of the apical papilla (SCAP).

Tooth avulsion

Topical antibiotic application on a tooth to be replanted after avulsion is also advocated to enhance healing. Moreover, the use of topical antibiotics has been reported to be more beneficial compared with systemic antibiotics in avulsion cases. This approach was supported by a study using replanted monkey teeth where inflammatory root resorption was significantly arrested by the use of topical doxycycline.

There is evidence that antibiotics may be important to control infection and to reduce the risk of inflammatory resorption. As inflammatory root resorption is one of the major challenges faced by clinicians during the management of a replanted tooth, topical antibiotic administration might serve as a helpful means to eliminate this undesirable complication. The IADT guidelines indicate that topical application of tetracyclines (minocycline or doxycycline, 1 mg per 20 mL of saline for 5 min) onto the root surface before reimplantation appears experimentally to have a beneficial effect, increasing the chance of pulpal space revascularization and periodontal healing in avulsed immature teeth with open apices.

To be continued.....